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The Impact of Cloud Computing on Employee Creativity in Egypt: Empirical Study

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Abstract

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of how cloud computing can be leveraged to enhance employee creativity in the Egyptian organizations. The research offers valuable insights and practical recommendations, serving as a roadmap for businesses in Egypt to, effectively, transition to cloud computing and harness its potential to drive innovation and competitiveness. Cloud computing has rapidly become a cornerstone of modern technology, offering great potential for organizations aiming to innovate and compete globally. Despite its promise, many organizations, particularly in Egypt, have yet to adopt cloud computing or fully exploit its benefits. This study investigates the impact of various dimensions of cloud computing cloud application, cloud management, cloud infrastructure, and cloud resources on employee creativity. The choice of this topic is motivated by the fact that the Egyptian companies have to increase their competitive advantage in both technological development and innovative practices. Currently, there is a challenge in understanding how cloud computing can, effectively, be put into practice in enhancing organizational capability, as well as employee creativity. Currently, organizations face significant challenges in cloud computing technologies adoption and optimization, which presents an opportunity to gain a competitive advantage within the fast-changing environment of technology. To address this research problem, a quantitative research methodology has been applied. Data collected through structured questionnaires were distributed among employees in different organizations in Egypt. This analysis is done to determine how important each dimension of cloud computing is in exploring employee creativity, which is an important and essential for keeping and maintaining modern competitive advantages in the global market

Keywords: *Cloud computing, employee creativity, cloud application, cloud management, cloud infrastructure, cloud resources.*

1. Introduction

The ideology of cloud computing gained popularity in 2007, thanks to the rapid development of communication channels and the increase in the geometric progression of the needs of both business and private users to expand their information systems.

The emergence of the term has begun to be discussed in 2008 at one of the thematic internet conferences. As a result of these discussions, different versions of cloud computing were proposed. The term cloud was used for the first time by the head of Google, Eric Schmidt and was further disseminated by the mass media.

Today, many companies, for example, Google, actively use the concept of cloud computing. The most typical example is Google Docs, which allows work with office documents.

Cloud computing has long been referred to as the fifth utility, following water, electricity, gas, and telephone services. It has revolutionized the ways computing is done for businesses and organizations or in private life. Such huge growth over the last few years is expected to further increase in the following years for individual and organizational purposes worldwide (Matias & Hernandez, 2021).

The role that clouds computing plays and the evolving creativity of humans are significant for corporate innovation and resilience in the fast-moving business world. As a fifth utility, this has revolutionized IT infrastructure and facilitated user collaboration, according to the perceptions of numerous observers (Matias & Hernandez, 2021; Kumari & Kaur, 2021). At the same time, individual creativity, embracing the generation and flourishing of new ideas, are elemental for corporate innovation and competitiveness (Slåtten et al., 2020).

Cloud computing benefits both individual and businesses, thereby increasing the output and efficiency of profitability alongside unmatched consumer convenience (Al Mudawi et al., 2022; Shahbaz & Zahid, 2022). As such, private users are more likely to embrace the use of cloud computing in managing large volumes of data, which could have a positive impact on their productivity and gains (Islam, 2019). Creativity expectations, conceived as the belief in the utility and efficiency of using the technology, creates the intentions among the users of cloud-based services within their ranks (Andrews et al., 2021; Kabra et al., 2023). Adoption of the services in cloud computing minimizes personal customers' financial constraints due to its low acquisition cost and pay-as-you-go expense billing model (Iranmanesh & Najji, 2021; Ali et al., 2021).

In fact, the cost effectuation strategy for cloud computing are relatedly important to the two sectors: firms and individuals, as reflected in research findings describing a positive relationship between cost savings and intention to use cloud computing services (Modisane & Jokonya, 2021; Asiaei & Nor, 2019). At the same time, creativity has come to be understood as essential for the survival of the organization; it impacts business performance and has been viewed as a source of generating creativity at work (Sanjeet et al., 2021; Cowling et al., 2015). Because creativity affects worker performance and market success, businesses, specifically SME businesses, value it (Joyner, 2017; Miah & Hafit, 2020).

Collaboration and IT infrastructure have seen massive transformations to cloud computing. As per NIST Sanjeev and Natrajan (2020) and Wu et al. (2020), cloud computing is a concept that facilitates effortless, on-demand network access to a shared pool of programmable computing resources, which includes Software as a Service (SaaS). SaaS, a vital part of companies' IT strategies, offers a number of advantages, such as reduced IT maintenance costs and improved collaboration (Fauscette, 2013).

2. Literature Review

Employee Creativity

Employee creativity is a creative employee who remains updated with new work methods and possesses the ability to solve complex problems with a sharp mind (Siddiqi & Qureshi, 2016). There is extensive evidence that employee creativity is a crucial factor for attaining high levels of innovation performance (Zhang et al., 2021). Creativity and innovation play vital roles in the success of any organization (Anderson et al., 2014), with creativity often used interchangeably with innovation (Slåtten et al., 2020). Initial research on creativity and innovation focuses on intellectual variables (Batey et al., 2009).

In the era of information technology, humanity depends on IT to accomplish their personal and professional prerequisites (Kapoor et al., 2023). This implies advanced software and storage facilities that represent great investments in IT infrastructure but are quite hard for individual users to put in place and maintain (Kumari & Kaur, 2021).

Cloud Application

Cloud-based applications have substantially enhanced the industry by offering several advantages, including reduced IT maintenance costs, improved collaboration, scalability, and on-demand accessibility (Sanjeev & Natrajan, 2020; Wu et al., 2020). Cloud apps and Software as a Service (SaaS) have evolved into a fundamental aspect of companies' IT strategies. What initially started with integrated functions (like talent management and sales force automation) has now expanded to encompass a diverse range of businesses, breaking the traditional boundaries for enterprise IT cloud architecture (Fauscette, 2013).

The trend of moving applications to the cloud, especially using Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) clouds, is growing in various industries. This shift is driven by benefits like lower ownership costs, increased flexibility, and the ability to easily adjust resources to match needs (RightScale, 2018). In the world of cloud setups, it is crucial, for users, to know exactly how well their applications are performing.

H1. Cloud application is positively correlated to employee creativity.

Cloud Management

Besides, Ting Si et al. (2014) positioned cloud computing as an optimal technology solution to address and alleviate the inefficiencies inherent in business operations. Their assessment identified that cloud computing is a transformative force that effectively addresses business challenges and fosters innovation. By integrating different services, cloud computing emerges as a catalyst to creativity and, hence, increases productivity levels.

In parallel, Zied et al. (2014) outlined the different functionalities of cloud computing, highlighting the role of cloud computing in the management and communication domain. Cloud computing is robust physical IT infrastructure which can be provided to organizations for seamless operational processes. This integration of cloud computing takes on a critical stand in the contemporary organizational environment, offering a holistic and synergistic platform for all-round management and communication.

H2. Cloud management has significant impact on employee creativity.

Cloud Infrastructure

That said, cloud computing services help in reducing the initial cost of business implementation, in its payment model, which is pay-as-you-go (Modisane & Jokonya, 2021). Cost savings and the intention to use cloud computing are positively related by Asiaei and Nor (2019). Therefore, Qasem et al. (2020) further supported that the fact of cost-effectiveness was only statistically significant between the intention to adopt cloud computing. In addition, Moses et al. (2021), they posited that the evolution of users' cost-effectiveness directly impacts the adoption of cloud computing.

Cloud computing technology is a completely novel and significant paradigm shift in relation to traditional business operations (Wang et al., 2016). The cloud is an extraordinary technical solution that creates a scene where companies are able to grow in a continuously changing environment. It enables organizations to use unique market attributes, including stability, cost-effectiveness, and performance optimization. The five essential characteristics are as follows in human terms:

- **Broad Network Access:**
- **Rapid Elasticity:**
- **Measured Service:**
- **On-Demand Self-Service:**
- **Resource Pooling:**

H3. Cloud infrastructure has significant impact on employee creativity.

Cloud Resources

In this regard, strategic planning becomes even more critical as it offers an effective way to apply cloud services, leverage returns on investment, and generate tangible returns, such as higher profits and intangible returns, such as business value as well as employee productivity and satisfaction (Irjashj, 2021). This does not include the view of cloud migration as only a simple activity but a means of modernizing applications in such a way that it needs to be effective and cost-efficient. For instance, many companies have taken varying routes for optimizing hardware, software, and services by using some leading IT vendors. While there are visible advantages in cloud migration, challenges will be expected during the move of a legacy application to new capabilities. The language of these difficulties should be in that of the one which the business team will be able to understand and relate to cost investments, improvements, and overall business performance.

IT staff should further use the products and services to improve security, help customers, and expand to new markets. It is formulated as a customized strategy swiftly; it begins with moving to the cloud, starting with small workloads, and focusing on demonstrating business value from achievable milestones at the very beginning. By focusing on these achievements, learning, and developing the cloud experience and expertise gradually, the IT team will learn and develop the cloud gradually. The range of cloud applications includes big data, analytics, web applications, third-party applications, collaboration tools, and productivity tools among others (NIST, 2011).

Cloud Essential Attributes

The essential attributes of cloud computing, explained by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) are as follows (Grance, et al., 2011):

- **On-Demand Self-Service (Pay-as-You-Use)**
- **Broad Network Access**
- **Resource Pooling (Multi-Tenancy)**
- **Rapid Elasticity**
- **Measured Service**

Cloud Computing Services Delivery Models

In the field of cloud computing, three principal service delivery models have gained prominence, collectively known as the SPI model: Software as a Service (SaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) (Diaby et al., 2017).

- **Software as a Service (SaaS)**
- **Platform as a Service (PaaS)**
- **Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS)**

Cloud Computing Deployment Models

This makes the right selection of a cloud deployment model very crucial for an institution while ensuring a smooth implementation process (Diaby et al., 2017). Chauhan et al. (2012) contended that this is a source of mistakes; in most instances, poor cloud selection stems from an ill-fit choice of a cloud type. Institutes should approach the process of detailed data so that they can identify which deployment model is most appropriate for them to stay clear of possible failings. However, while embracing cloud services, many organizations tend to overlook the security concern, over-relying too much on the security measures that are embedded in cloud platforms. This oversight invites malicious actors to exploit vulnerabilities and compromise the systems of multiple tenants. The four models (public cloud, private cloud, community cloud, and hybrid cloud) have gained significant consideration to various cloud-based systems, matching requirements for management and the nature of the data being handled.

- Public Cloud
- Private Cloud
- Community Cloud
- Hybrid Cloud

H4. Cloud resources has significant impact on employee creativity.

Figure 1: Conceptual model proposed by the researcher.

3. Research Objectives

- To what extent does the adoption of cloud base applications impact the creativity of employees.
- The efficiency in management practices considers cloud-enabled enhancements for an environment which can support creativity.
- To determine ways in which robust scalable cloud infrastructure enables innovation.
- To see that the accessibility and efficiency of cloud resources would enable employees to execute creative projects and initiatives.
- To identify the strategic implications of cloud computing for organizations

4. Research Methodology

Research Design

The researcher uses a quantitative approach based on the administration of a questionnaire. A set of closed-ended questions was used to collect the data.

Sampling Strategy and Size

Given the lack of sampling frame providing information on the size of the target population and its characteristics, the minimum sample size should be targeted is 384. The "sample size" is 384 employees as a minimum level. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009) confirmed when the population is one million, the "sample size" will be 384 members at 95% "confidence level" and 5% "margin of error" supposing that the "data" are gathered from all members in the selected sample. Therefore, this "sample size" should be adequate for the statistical analysis and consistent with the homogeneity of the targeted population.

During the data collection period, a total of 484 responses were received. Based on the screening questions, 103 respondents did not finalize all questions or said they do not implement cloud computing in their work, or they are not located in Egypt (which represent 21.2% from total responses). As a consequence, a total of 381 valid surveys were analyzed in this study, which represented 78.8% of the total number of responses received.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

In this section, the demographic profile of the respondents is summarized; it covers the gender, age group, and employment sector.

According to the demographics, women make up 26% of the respondents, and men make up 74% of the sample. In terms of age, the bulk of respondents fall into three age groups: 18-29 years old (22%), 30-39 years old (40%), and 40-49 years old (32%).

In terms of employment, 30% of the respondents reported working in manufacturing, followed by 18% who reported working in healthcare.

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Demography	Category	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	283	74
	Female	98	26
Age	Less than 18	2	.5
	18-29 years	82	22
	30-39 years	153	40
	40-49 years	121	32
	50-59 years	21	5.5
	60+ years	2	.5
Sector of Employment	Manufacturing	113	30
	Healthcare	70	18
	Education	51	13
	(Don't want to answer)	32	8
	Technology/IT	31	8
	Finance	25	7
	Service	22	6
	Construction	16	4
	Retail	15	4
Other (please specify)	6	2	

Source: Results of Statistical Analysis.

Data Collection Tool and Sampling Strategy

A scale used in survey research, to gauge respondents' opinions, is the Likert scale. Likert scale questions are closed-ended, single-choice questions. The main advantage of employing a Likert scale over a basic yes/no question type is that it gives more detailed information about people's opinions towards a subject. Researchers can evaluate different degrees of agreement, relevance, quality, and other variables by utilizing a Likert scale. As for the questionnaire development, all the research variables items are to be measured on a five-point Likert scale (Likert, 1932).

Most surveys were designed to evaluate attitudes and perceptions that cannot be ascertained by outside observation employ a Likert scale. Interval data that can further assist inferential statistical tests is what the Likert scale is meant to display. Because the Likert scale produces numerical data that can be evaluated to assess the research study's assumptions, its usage is consistent with the quantitative methodologies that guided the research design of this study (Holt, 2014).

The questionnaire consists of two sections. The first section will be demographic questions and another set of questions validate and ensure employees' using cloud computing tools. The second section will measure the research variables (4 independent variables and 1 dependent variable). All the variables' items, in the second section, are rated in a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The first section will be measured by a nominal scale.

The survey was taken from two articles, the first is "Does Cloud Computing Improve Employees' Creativity and Team Performance?" (Zou & Jian, 2022); it is used for independent variables. The second research is "A New Conceptual Model for Assessing the Role of Knowledge Cloud in Stimulating Subordinate Creativity" (Xiao & Wang, 2023). This will be working on dependent variable, employee creativity.

In the first pilot, there are some adjustments that have been done on questions to simplify wording for targeting sample; those changes have been done based on a pilot questionnaire and get feedback before implementing the survey on the final phase.

In light of the feedback, the questionnaire was distributed to a number of respondents in a pilot phase after which refinement and simplification were made to the questions. The adjustments were done with the intent that clear questions would ensure accurate feedback from the respondents. Questions perceived to be unclear were reformulated to be more direct and easier to understand. Moreover, certain questions were deleted to streamline the questionnaire. Such adjustments were done to make the responses more qualitative and reliable. The following is a table showing the slightly changes that have been done.

5. Data analysis

Data Cleaning

During the data collection period, a total of 484 responses were received. Based on the screening questions, 103 respondents did not finalize all questions or said they do not implement cloud computing in their work, or they are not located in Egypt which represent 21.2% from total responses. This means that as a result, the total number of people who participated or answered the survey in this study was 381 which represent 78.8%.

Goodness of Measures

Tests for validity and reliability were completed before additional analysis were conducted. Factor analysis was used to evaluate the instruments' construct validity (Hair et al., 2010).

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Items CA2, CI3, and CR2 were eliminated from the model as a consequence of the CFA, and the model was recreated since the factor loads were low (See table 2 and figure 1).

Table 2: Factor Loading

Item	Variables	Factor loading Model 1	Factor loading Model 2
CA1	Cloud Application	0.96	0.96
CA2	Cloud Application	0.43	
CA3	Cloud Application	0.70	0.69
CA4	Cloud Application	0.70	0.69
CM1	Cloud Management	0.73	0.73
CM2	Cloud Management	0.62	0.62
CM3	Cloud Management	0.58	0.57
CM4	Cloud Management	0.68	0.68
CI1	Cloud Infrastructure	0.74	0.73
CI2	Cloud Infrastructure	0.53	0.52
CI3	Cloud Infrastructure	0.43	
CI4	Cloud Infrastructure	0.80	0.80

CR1	Cloud Resource	0.78	0.77
CR2	Cloud Resource	0.34	
CR3	Cloud Resource	0.70	0.70
CR4	Cloud Resource	0.87	0.87
EC1	Employee Creativity	0.98	0.96
EC2	Employee Creativity	0.58	0.58
EC3	Employee Creativity	0.69	0.68
EC4	Employee Creativity	0.75	0.75
EC5	Employee Creativity	0.69	0.69
EC6	Employee Creativity	0.73	0.73

Source: Results of Statistical Analysis.

Figure 2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis Models

Model 1

Model 2

Source: Results of Statistical Analysis.

Reliability Test

Table 3 shows the Cronbach alpha for the scale. The Cronbach alpha is greater than 0.8, which indicates that the scale is reliable.

Table 3: Cronbach's Alpha for Questionnaire

Variable	No of items	Cronbach's Alpha
Cloud Application	3	.799
Cloud Management	4	.629
Cloud Infrastructure	3	.565
Cloud Resource	3	.669
Employee Creativity	6	.811
Questionnaire	19	.889

Source: Results of Statistical Analysis.

Central Tendency and Dispersion

Employees' Creativity

In this context, the researcher will explain the results of the descriptive analysis of the dependent variable employees' creativity. The averages of the answers for all sample items range between (4.35) and (4.47), which means that the answers tended towards strongly agree (See table 5).

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics for The Employees' Creativity

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
EC1	381	1.00	5.00	4.4249	.04153	.81595
EC2	381	1.00	5.00	4.4715	.03364	.66094
EC3	381	1.00	5.00	4.3964	.03579	.70316
EC4	381	1.00	5.00	4.3912	.03794	.74543
EC5	381	1.00	5.00	4.4067	.03661	.71920
EC6	381	1.00	5.00	4.3549	.03903	.76680
Employee Creativity	381	1.00	5.00	4.4076	.02725	.53542

Source: Results of Statistical Analysis

Cloud Computing

To calculate the descriptive analysis of the independent variable represented by cloud computing, the researcher calculated the highest value, the lowest value, the mean, the standard deviation, and the standard error. All values range between 1 and 5, which indicates that there are no outliers. (See table 4). The sample size was 381, which means that there are no missing data. On the other hand, the average for all dimensions ranged between 4.40 and 4.60. This means that the study sample's answer tends towards strongly agree in all dimensions. In the next section, the researcher will explain each dimension separately and in order.

The results of Table (4) indicate that the responses of the study sample of *cloud application* ranged between 1 and 5, with a general mean (4.60), i.e., (strongly agree). In this dimension, the mean items ranged from (4.45) to (4.71). These means fall within the response categories strongly agree (5) and agree (4). The two highest items came as follows: the item "CA1" (I believe that rapidly introducing new products like OneDrive or SharePoint is a top advantage of cloud computing for the organization I work in) with a mean (4.71) and (strongly agree). This is followed by the item "CA3" (There are advantages of using cloud computing system SaaS (Software as a service) such as OneDrive and SharePoint), with a mean (4.64) and (strongly agree).

The last item came as follows: the item "CA4" (One of the advantages of using cloud computing is that I am able to test any new application in a secured way), with a mean (4.45) and (strongly agree).

The next dimension was cloud management. In this dimension, the averages of the answers ranged between 4.47 and 4.50. This indicates that the sample agreed towards strongly agree, the two highest items came as follows: the item "CM1" (The advantage of using cloud computing is the increase in Productivity, with a mean (4.57) and (strongly agree). This is followed by the item "CM3" (It is expected that with the use of cloud computing services, the degree of flexibility in the technology sector will increase), with a mean (4.49) and (strongly agree).

This is proceeded by cloud infrastructure; it reached the mean (4.48) (see table 7). The average responses for the sample ranged (4.50) and (4.47); the highest item came as follows: the item " CI4" (I believe that the organization that I work in has all the necessary infrastructure to use cloud computing services) with a mean (4.50). This is followed by (CI1) (I believe that the organization that I work I considers cost saving on hardware as the most important advantage of cloud computing) and (CI2) (The advantages of using cloud computing are powerful server capabilities) with a mean (4.47).

The final dimension was cloud resource; it reached the mean (4.40). This indicates that the sample agreed towards strongly agree. In this dimension, there are three questions: the highest question came as follows (CR4) (Given the resources and knowledge required, using cloud computing services will be easy), with a mean of (4.43). The lowest item was (CR1) (One of the most important advantages of cloud computing is that it does not need a significant upfront investment), with a mean (4.37).

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics for the Cloud Computing

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
CA1	381	1.00	5.00	4.7176	.03072	.60350
CA3	381	1.00	5.00	4.6451	.03007	.59079
CA4	381	1.00	5.00	4.4585	.03950	.77600
Cloud Application	381	1.00	5.00	4.6071	.02531	.49723
CM1	381	1.00	5.00	4.5777	.03158	.62037
CM2	381	1.00	5.00	4.4663	.03595	.70630
CM3	381	1.00	5.00	4.4974	.03245	.63756
CM4	381	1.00	5.00	4.4430	.03962	.77835
Cloud Management	381	1.00	5.00	4.4961	.02442	.47977
CI1	381	1.00	5.00	4.4793	.03988	.78349
CI2	381	1.00	5.00	4.4741	.03072	.60354
CI4	381	1.00	5.00	4.5026	.03636	.71441
Cloud Infrastructure	381	1.00	5.00	4.4853	.02628	.51633
CR1	381	1.00	5.00	4.3756	.04267	.83826
CR3	381	1.00	5.00	4.4145	.03319	.65203
CR4	381	1.00	5.00	4.4378	.03566	.70066
Cloud Resource	381	1.00	5.00	4.4093	.02901	.57004

Source: Results of Statistical Analysis.

Testing Hypotheses

The study hypotheses are the following:

H1. There is a Positive Significant Relationship (0.444**) between Cloud application and employee creativity.

H2. There is a Positive Significant Relationship (0.556**) between Cloud management and employee creativity.

H3. There is a Positive Significant Relationship (0.562**) between Cloud infrastructure and employee creativity.

H4. There is a Positive Significant Relationship (0.579**) between Cloud resources and employee creativity.

Table 6: Pearson Correlation Analysis between Research Variables

	Cloud application	Cloud management	Cloud infrastructure	Cloud resources	employee creativity
Cloud application					
Cloud management	0.572** .000				
Cloud infrastructure	0.547** .000	0.603** .000			
Cloud resources	0.559** .000	0.505** .000	0.597** .000		
employee creativity	0.444** .000	0.556** .000	0.562** .000	0.579** .000	

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Results of Statistical Analysis.

Proposed Predictive Model

In tables 7 and 8, the value of the F test reached 78.476; it is less than 0.05 and is statistically significant. The result, therefore, indicates that there is a significant relative contribution of implementing cloud computing on employees' creativity. The value of R² measures the effect size or relative contribution of independent variables, cloud application, cloud management, cloud infrastructure, and cloud resource on dependent variable, employees' creativity. The value was 0.452, in Egypt; cloud computing influences 45% of creativity with regard to the employees.

Table 7: Results of Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.672	.452	.446	.398

Predictors: (Constant), Cloud Application, Cloud Management, Cloud Infrastructure, and Cloud Resource

Source: Results of Statistical Analysis.

Table 8: Results of ANOVA test

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	49.857	4	12.464	78.476	.000
	Residual	60.512	381	.159		
	Total	110.37	385			

Dependent Variable: employees' creativity

Predictors: (Constant), Cloud Application, Cloud Management, Cloud Infrastructure, and Cloud Resource.

Source: Results of Statistical Analysis

To find out the effect of each cloud computing factor on employees' creativity, regression coefficients were calculated, and the results were as follows:

From the coefficients in table (9), the researcher sees that the Cloud Application (β_1 (-0.05)) is not significant since the p-value is 0.932. For this reason, the first hypothesis that was rejected.

The Cloud Management (β_2 (0.302)) is significant since the p-value is 0.000. In addition, cloud infrastructure (β_3 = 0.220) is significant since the p-value is 0.000. Cloud resources are significant since the p-value is 0.000. β_4 = 0.298 is significant since the p-value is 0.000.

Given the coefficients (β_1 = -0.05, β_2 = 0.302, β_3 = 0.220, β_4 = 0.298 \neq 0), with the betas not equal to zero (A coefficient of 0 means that the values of the dependent variable do not consistently differ as the values of the independent variable increase.). For this reason, the second, third, and fourth hypotheses were accepted. So, the researcher's acceptance of the main hypothesis is a partial acceptance as:

There is a Positive Significant impact to Cloud computing on employees' creativity.

Table 9: Results of the Coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	β	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.769	.221		3.479	.000
Cloud Application	-0.05	.055	-0.004	0.086	.932
Cloud Management	0.302	.057	0.271	5.269	.000
Cloud Infrastructure	0.220	.055	0.212	3.977	.000
Cloud Resource	0.298	0.48	0.318	6.261	.000

Dependent Variable: employees' creativity

Source: Results of Statistical Analysis

6. Conclusions

This presented the critical challenge of organizations remaining competitive and creative. On the search for innovation, cloud computing emerged as a lighthouse for new possibilities and horizons. Many organizations, though, remained skeptical of the benefits and practical effect on employee creativity.

It is in this need to discover detailed study. The journey began by understanding the potential of cloud computing in enhancing the capability of an organization and spreading over four key dimensions: cloud application, cloud management, cloud infrastructure, and cloud resources. Each represented a piece of the puzzle that, when put together, opened new doors of creativity within the workplace.

The research was set out to understand how these dimensions influence employee creativity. A response questionnaire was sent out to employees from various sectors in Egypt, collecting valuable insights into their experiences and perceptions. The data collected on this element of the research work clearly described the technological landscape of these organizations.

The first revelation came in the dimension of cloud applications. Very much expected and responded positively in the questionnaires, the statistical analysis returned no direct effect on employee creativity.

The cloud management, infrastructure, and resource dimensions were diametrically opposite to this scenario. These drivers became strong catalysts for creativity in themselves. Good cloud management practices are ensured to have the environment in which employees could freely explore new ideas, unconstrained by administrative tasks. Strong and scalable cloud infrastructure means unobstructed operations so that employees' creativity is focused on the core competencies. Easy and efficient cloud resources empower them to take on ambitious projects that require much computer power and storage.

Over time, it became certain that ingenuity lay in the move away from traditional in-house hosting to the cloud-based systems, principally through the Software as a Service model. This approach to the digital transformation was incomparably different due to its flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and scalability, from any other technique employed by another organizations.

The journey, however, was not without its limitations. First, the focus on the setting of the Egyptian organizations probably limited the generalizability of the findings. The use of self-reported data introduced potential biases into the study design. The cross-sectional design prevents inferences related to long-term impacts. Secondly, cost management optimization was and is still a main challenge for organizations embarking on this journey.

Employee Creativity

The proposed hypothesis of the study was that there would be a positive association between cloud application and employees' creativity, indicating that the usage of cloud-based applications will enhance creativity. However, the result obtained, from the hypothesis, indicates that there is no direct impact, and hence it has been rejected. This shows that although cloud application may not be used to directly increase employee creativity in Egypt, other factors in the organization may be responsible for the employee creativity. Further study areas would propose other factors that lead to employees' creativity.

Cloud Application

The hypothesis testing result showed that the cloud application has no direct influence on the creativity of employees, which was against the expected results. From this, the organization may be using cloud-based applications alone, which cannot reflect on creativity of employees. It is also important to recognize that cloud applications have more general use than creativity-related application, such as data storage and collaboration. Organizations should continue applying the cloud applications for their intended purposes and adopt different strategies in enhancing the creativity of employees.

Cloud Management

The research reveals that there is a significant positive impact of evidence for supporting the hypothesis that cloud management has a significant positive impact on employee creativity. This shows that the efficiency of cloud management and processes directly impacts the employee creativity. Organizations should invest in a well-placed cloud management system, security features, and access controls to engage and nurture employee creativity. Add to this, the fostering teamwork and communication to encourage ideas' generation and exchange of knowledge.

Cloud Infrastructure

The results of this study confirm that cloud infrastructure impacts employee creativity. This means that the availability of infrastructure elements that support cloud computing services directly impacts the employee creativity. Therefore, organizations must invest in a strong infrastructure base that would ensure reliable and efficient services so that it helps in being creative and innovative. Moreover, organizations have to review their infrastructure and perform updates according to the emerging trends in technology and changes in business needs.

Cloud Resources

The hypothesis testing points out that cloud resources are affecting employees' creativity, and the direction of the effect is positive and significant. In such case, the implication would be that the organization should adequately provide resources, including financial investment and technical expertise, in support of cloud initiatives. Organizations have to invest adequate resources towards adoption and use cloud technologies that enhance the creativity of employees and, hence, enhance organizational performance. Furthermore, organizations must be willing to provide training and development opportunities; that is to say, employees are

equipped with the requisite skill sets and knowledge base, which can be used towards using cloud resources for creative purposes efficiently.

In that line, it happened that the factor of cloud application has no direct impact on the level of employee creativity. Nonetheless, the factors, such as cloud management, cloud infrastructure, and cloud resources have significant positive impact. This means that good management, infrastructure, and resource allocation are the key motivators in making creative employee within the organizational system. Actually, investment in those areas is likely to result in fertile ground for innovation and competitive advantage. However, creativity is a result of many factors, and as such organizations should take an integrated approach to foster creativity among employees.

This journey does not end here as further research in new dimensions is required, and, at the same time, addressing the identified limitations is essential. On the other hand, the present study stands out to testify to the transformation potential of cloud computing in a modern workplace and further offers valuable insights and strategic guidance for organizations focusing on innovation in the digital age.

7. Limitations

Therefore, one can get a deeper understanding of the relationship of cloud technology to employee creativity in various scenarios. Resolving these constraints and broadening the focus of future study can develop more specialized and successful methods for using cloud computing to boost creativity throughout the world.

First, Sample Size and Generalizability: the conclusions of the study can be generalized since they come from a generalized sample. Future research should narrow the scope of the fields and sample sizes.

Second, Cloud Technology Scope: A wide range of cloud technologies were under investigation. Future research could explore certain specific areas of cloud computing at greater length to give more accurate observations.

Third, Measuring Creativity: Subjective judgment is one way that creativity can be measured. Further research that integrates qualitative and quantitative methods could lead to a fuller picture.

Fourth, Geographic Scope: The research was targeting only Egyptian enterprises. While giving insightful information on how cloud technologies would impact employee creativity in this specific environment, it limits the applicability of the findings to other areas or nations. The relationship between cloud technologies and employee creativity can be moderated by regional differences in technical infrastructure, cultural views on creativity, and the rate of adoption of cloud technologies.

Fifth, Data Collected Using a Questionnaire: To be more specific, through the questionnaire, it looks at attitudes rather than facts. This can be considered a limitation.

Sixth, Enough studies: On the impact of cloud computing on team performance and employee innovation. Thus, a limited number of studies can be compared with the findings of the present inquiry.

Seventh, Cost Management Optimization: Complexity in cloud computing that can lead to hidden expenses and challenges in maintaining the budget due to the variable and dynamic pricing models of cloud services.

8. Suggestions for Future Research

These follow-up study recommendations provide more elaborated explanations of the research findings and could help in further in-depth understandings of the relationship between cloud computing and worker creativity. They can help businesses in comprehending how to utilize cloud computing to build a creative and innovative work environment.

- *Evaluate Employee Adaptation:* Examine the ability of employees to adjust to these new technologies that are based on the cloud and the role of training in this process.
- *Conduct Cross-National Studies:* In order to find out if the results applied in different cultural and economic situations, future research should include firms from different geographic areas. This would go a long way to understanding the generalizability of the findings.
- *Regional Comparisons:* Comparing businesses in Egypt with those in other regions to see if there is any regional differentiation in the use of cloud technologies with regard to employee creativity. The purpose is to identify geographical factors that may influence the effectiveness of cloud computing.
- *Cultural Influence on Creativity:* Analyze how cultural differences influence how cloud technologies are used and the effects they have on creativity. Understanding the cultural impacts can be used to tailor the deployment of cloud technologies for the improvement of creativity across different cultural settings.
- *Improvement of Cloud apps:* Seek ways of improving cloud apps, which could tangentially drive creativity. One could research how to integrate cloud apps with more cloud management resources and capabilities for a more cohesive environment that will encourage innovation.
- *Training and Development Programs:* Analyze the effectiveness of various training and development programs aimed at developing employees in their ability to make innovative uses of cloud technology. This includes workshops, online courses, and on-site training.
- *Collaboration Tools and Techniques:* Investigate how specific tools and methodologies of collaboration can spur creativity in cloud-based environments. This can involve comparing the different tools and their impact on the development of ideas and teamwork.
- *Employee Adoption and Adaptation:* Understand how employees adopt and adapt the new cloud technology. Studies could be conducted around; such factors as organizational support, design of the user experience, and training of personnel to ensure seamless adaption.
- *Cycles of Feedback and Improvement:* Analyze how frequent feedback and improvement cycles help to make the best utilization of cloud technology for creative purposes. This will involve the research into how incremental changes and continuous feedback loops foster creativity.
- Look at how mobile cloud apps help remote work and how they affect the creativity and teamwork of employees.
- Investigate how immersive technologies (augmented reality and virtual reality) can enhance user creativity in cloud-based collaborative environments.
- Examine how cloud applications may integrate machine learning and data analytics to offer personalized suggestions and insights in support of creativity.
- Examine how data privacy issues and cybersecurity precautions affect users' trust, confidence, and propensity to interact creatively in cloud settings.

Future studies could focus on the intermediate variables between cloud elements and employee creativity: namely, how job characteristics, organizational culture, and leadership principles moderate the relationship between cloud computing and creativity. Understanding these mediating factors could help organizations develop targeted initiatives to effectively enhance creativity and provide deeper insights into the mechanisms by which cloud elements influence creativity. Investigating the way in which individual differences, such as personality characteristics and thinking styles, moderate the relationship between cloud technologies and creativity may provide insightful information about how businesses can adapt their strategies to encourage creativity among a diverse workforce. These techniques of mixed-methods approaches, such as quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, could provide a deep understanding of the convoluted interplay at work.

Future studies could evaluate the role that user experience (UX) design plays in cloud apps, and how it affects user creativity and productivity. This may consider how aspects, such as responsiveness, navigation, interface design, and user customization options, impact the holistic user experience and, in turn, productivity and user creativity. The different methods used to carry out research from a user-centered perspective in

usability testing and user interviewing may help pinpoint design elements that help improve productivity, creativity, and engagement. Research into how emerging technologies, such as augmented reality and artificial intelligence, are adopted in cloud applications and how this in turn impacts creativity can be a source of crucial new insight into the future development of cloud-based productivity tools.

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